

1 **OMITTING DRY OFF NEGATIVELY AFFECTS LACTATION IN DAIRY GOATS**

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3 **Caja**

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5 Multiparous dairy goats were dried off for 2 mo before kidding or continuously milked
6 without dry off. Most of the goats (63%) stopped lactation by themselves and dried off
7 spontaneously for nearly 1 mo before kidding. Goats without dry off had kids with low birth
8 weight, produced immunologically poor colostrum, and lost more than 20% of milk yield in
9 the subsequent lactation. Omitting the dry off period is not recommended in dairy goats.

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OMITTING THE DRY OFF IN DAIRY GOATS

**Omitting the Dry Off Period Negatively Affects Colostrum and Milk Yield
in Dairy Goats**

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ABSTRACT

Seventeen pregnant multiparous Murciano-Granadina dairy goats, kept in a semi-intensive exploitation system with once daily milking throughout lactation and 1 kidding per year (milk yield, 577 L in 300 d), were used to study the effects of dry off period length on performances in the subsequent lactation. Goats were mated at wk 29 of lactation and were assigned to 2 experimental groups according to dry off treatment: goats that were dried off 56 d before expected kidding (D56; n = 9) and goats without dry off (D0; n = 8). After parturition, kids were removed from their mothers and weighed before sucking. Goats were hand milked to obtain colostrums and machine milked thereafter. Colostrum was sampled for composition and IgG analysis. Milk yield was recorded weekly during the preceding and subsequent lactations. Udders were biopsied in a sample of goats at d -65 (late lactation), d -49 d (during dry off) and d 48 (early lactation) to kidding (d 0). Apoptotic and proliferating cells in mammary tissues were detected immunohistochemically. Five goats (63%) in the D0 group dried off spontaneously at 27 ± 4 d before kidding, and were considered separately (D27). The rest of the D0 goats yielded 0.86 L/d from d -56 to kidding. Goats kidded 2.25 kids/goat, but D0 kids had lesser birth weight (1.7 kg) than D27 (2.2 kg) and D56 (2.1 kg). Colostrum of D0 goats contained less IgG (5.6 mg/mL) than D27 (32.9 mg/mL) and D56 (42.4 mg/mL). In the following lactation (210 d), D0 goats produced less milk (1.78 L/d) than D27 (2.51 L/d) and D56 (2.24 L/d), with no differences between D27 and D56. Apoptosis and proliferation indices increased from 0.51 and 2.09%, at d -65, to 1.75 and 7.12% at d -49 (d 7 of dry off) in D56 goats. Despite differences in daily milk yield at early lactation (d 48) between D0, D27 and D56 groups (1.73, 2.68, and 2.53 L/d; respectively), no differences in apoptosis or proliferation indices were detected (D0, 0.65 and 2.48%; D27, 0.68 and 1.37%; and, D56, 0.71 and 2.95%), indicating that dry period length did not affect mammary cell turnover in the subsequent lactation. Omitting the dry period between lactations reduced the quality of

47 colostrums and had negative effects on milk yield in dairy goats. Goats dried off
48 spontaneously for 27 d were as productive as goats dried for 56 d, indicating that less than 2
49 mo of drying off may be enough in practice.

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51 **Key Words:** continuous milking, apoptosis, lactogenesis, dairy goat

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INTRODUCTION

54 A non lactating dry period before parturition is believed necessary to permit replacement
55 of damaged or senescent epithelial cells (Capuco et al., 1997), and hence to maximize milk
56 production during the ensuing lactation. Omitting the dry period in dairy cows reduced milk
57 yield by 15 to 25% in the subsequent lactation (Swanson, 1965; Remond et al., 1992; Rastani
58 et al., 2005), indicating that a dry period between lactations is indispensable for dairy cows.
59 Omitting the dry period accompanied with bST injection, [however](#), resulted in no loss of
60 production in multiparous cows, but in primiparous cows there was a loss (Annen et al.,
61 2004a). Available information indicates that the dry period seems to be unnecessary in dairy
62 goats. The only study carried out on multiparous goats with the half-udder design (Fowler et
63 al., 1991) showed that continuously milked half-udders were as productive as half-udders
64 with the dry period.

65 Acquisition of passive immunity by the neonate depends on consumption of a sufficient
66 amount of colostral IgG prior to cessation of macromolecular transport by the intestine (Stott
67 and Fellah, 1983). Continuous milking of 1 half-udder throughout the dry period in dairy
68 cows reduced the massive selective transfer of blood IgG into the colostrum of these glands
69 (Brandon and Lascelles, 1975). In contrast, colostrum formation was normal in the
70 contralateral, unmilked glands. These results show that there is a local regulation of colostrum
71 formation and indicate that local signals, such as continuous milking throughout the dry

72 period, can impede colostrogenesis, even during late gestation when hormonal influences
73 favor its establishment. If colostrum contains a low concentration of IgG, the neonate has to
74 be fed a large amount of colostrum to obtain a sufficient amount of IgG. Stott and Fellah
75 (1983), [however](#), suggested that large amounts of colostrum containing a low concentration of
76 IgG would not be absorbed adequately; instead limited amounts of colostrum with a high
77 concentration of IgG may be more beneficial. The effect of omitting the dry period on
78 colostrum quality has not been studied before in dairy goats.

79 Milk yield depends on the activity and number of mammary epithelial cells (Knight, 2000).
80 The number of mammary cells is determined by the rates of cell apoptosis and proliferation.
81 Apoptosis and proliferation occur in the mammary gland throughout lactation, resulting in a
82 considerable turnover of mammary cells (Capuco et al., 2001; Colitti et al., 2004). Capuco et
83 al. (2001) reported daily rates of proliferation and apoptosis in the bovine mammary gland of
84 0.3 and 0.56%, respectively. Assuming that these indices are constant throughout lactation
85 and that cells which die are not those which have proliferated, Capuco et al. (2001) calculated
86 that 90% of mammary cells are renewed during lactation. Moreover, they estimated that if
87 mammary cells die after proliferating, then more than half of the cells could renew themselves
88 during a 240-d lactation. Besides the stage of lactation, some management factors such as bST
89 injection (Capuco et al., 2001), milking frequency (Hale et al., 2003), and diet energy density
90 (Norgaard et al., 2005) affect the indices of mammary apoptosis and proliferation. It is not
91 known whether omitting the dry period can affect mammary cell turnover in the subsequent
92 lactation.

93 The objective of this study was to investigate the effects of omitting the dry period on
94 colostrum quality, milk yield, and mammary cell turnover in the subsequent lactation in
95 Murciano-Granadina goats.

96

MATERIALS AND METHODS

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98 The experimental procedures and animal care conditions were approved by the Ethical
99 Committee of Animal and Human Experimentation of the Universitat Autònoma de
100 Barcelona (reference CEEAH 400/2002).

101

Animals and Management Conditions

103 Seventeen pregnant multiparous Murciano-Granadina dairy goats from the herd of the
104 S1GCE (Servei de Granges i Camps Experimentals) of the Universitat Autònoma de
105 Barcelona were used. Goats were mated naturally at wk 29 of lactation (April) after estrus
106 induction by the buck effect. Eight wk before the expected kidding date (293 ± 0.6 DIM),
107 goats were assigned to 2 experimental groups: goats that were dried off for 56 d (**D56**; $n = 9$)
108 and goats without dry off (**D0**; $n = 8$). Five of the 8 goats assigned to the D0 group reduced
109 milk yield dramatically during pregnancy and dried off spontaneously at 27 ± 4 d before
110 kidding, and were thereafter considered as a separate group (**D27**). Values of age (4.0 ± 0.5 ,
111 4.0 ± 0.6 , and 3.7 ± 0.7 yr) and parity number (2.8 ± 0.4 , 3.0 ± 0.6 , and 2.7 ± 0.7) were similar
112 for D56, D27 and D0 goats, respectively. Goats grazed for 6 h daily and were supplemented
113 indoors with a commercial concentrate (6.4 MJ NE_L/kg and 160 g CP/kg; as fed) at a flat rate
114 of 0.5 to 1.0 kg/d according to lactation stage, and with 0.5 kg dehydrated alfalfa hay and 0.5
115 kg alfalfa pellets. During the end of pregnancy and drying off, the goats were maintained in
116 pens and fed with a dehydrated mixture of 50% maize-whole plant and 50% alfalfa ad libitum
117 and 0.3 kg/d of concentrate. Moreover, lactating goats received 0.5 kg/d of concentrate in the
118 milking parlor.

119 Goats were milked in a double-12 stall parallel milking parlor (Westfalia-Separator Ibérica,
120 Granollers, Spain) with recording jars ($2 \text{ L} \pm 5\%$) and a low milk pipeline. Milking machine
121 was set at a vacuum pressure of 42 kPa, a pulsation rate of 90 pulses/min, and a pulsation

122 ratio of 66%. Milking routine included machine milking, stripping before cluster removal, and
123 teat dipping in an iodine solution (P3-cide plus, Henkel Hygiene, Barcelona, Spain).

124

125 *Sample Collection, Analysis and Measurements*

126 Milk yield was recorded weekly using the recording jars in the milking parlor until wk 30
127 of the subsequent lactation (wk 80 of the experiment). After parturition, kids were weighed
128 and separated from their mothers before sucking. Goats were hand milked, and fresh
129 colostrum samples were collected to determine specific gravity (**SG**) and colostrum
130 composition. For the IgG concentration, colostrum samples were frozen at -20 °C until
131 analysis. The SG of colostrum was measured using a density flask (Afora S.A., Madrid,
132 Spain) according to Lewis (1987). Colostrum TS were calculated by drying in an oven at 103
133 °C overnight. Fat was analyzed by the Gerber method. Non CN protein was measured by
134 Kjeldahl analysis of the filtrate after precipitation with 10% acetic acid and 1M sodium
135 acetate, and NPN was measured by Kjeldahl analysis of filtrate after precipitation with 20%
136 TCA (International Dairy Federation, 1993). Total protein was expressed as $N \times 6.38$, and CN
137 was calculated as the difference between total protein and non CN protein.

138 Concentration of IgG in the colostrum was determined by the radial immunodiffusion
139 technique using VET-RID kit plates specific for goat IgG (Bethyl Laboratories, Montgomery,
140 TX). Colostrum samples were diluted (1:10) using PBS (pH = 7.4) and then the wells on the
141 plates were filled with 5 μ L of diluted colostrum. Plates were incubated at room temperature
142 for 24 h, after which the diameters of the ring-shaped precipitates were measured to the
143 nearest tenth of a millimeter using a scaled ocular of a microscope (Olympus SZH, Olympus
144 Corporation, Tokyo, Japan). A reference curve was constructed by plotting the diameter of the
145 precipitated rings of 3 standard IgG concentrations (250, 1000, and 2000 mg/dL) on two-

146 cycle semilogarithmic graph paper. The concentration of IgG in the samples was determined
147 by interpolation from the reference curve.

148

149 *Mammary Biopsies and Immunohistochemistry*

150 Seven goats with similar BW (48.3 ± 1.3 kg) and milk yield (0.54 ± 0.19 L/d) at the end of
151 the preceding lactation were chosen for udder biopsy. Mammary biopsies of milked udders
152 were taken after subcutaneous local anesthesia (2 ml lidocaine 2%, B. Braun Medical,
153 Barcelona, Spain) and skin incision with a scalpel in a half udder by using a 14 gauge needle
154 (Bard Max-Core, Covington, GA). The biopsy needle was introduced approximately 3 cm in
155 the parenchyma 2 or 3 times to obtain sufficient tissue.

156 The first biopsy was obtained from the 7 chosen goats (3 D56 and 4 D0) at $d 284 \pm 1.6$ of
157 the preceding lactation. The second biopsy was programmed 7 d after the start of drying off
158 to compare lactation and involution in the same D56 goats. No biopsies were planned in the
159 D0 goats because no significant udder changes were expected after 1 wk of lactation.

160 Nevertheless, 3 of the 4 biopsied D0 animals did not maintain lactation and spontaneously
161 dried off, becoming the D27 non-lactating group. The last biopsy was obtained at $d 48 \pm 1.1$
162 of the subsequent lactation from 9 goats (3 goats in D56 biopsied twice previously, 3 goats in
163 D27 biopsied once previously, 1 goat in D0 biopsied once previously, and 2 goats in D0
164 biopsied for the first time).

165 Mammary samples were fixed in 10% neutral buffered formalin overnight at 4°C before
166 being transferred to 70% ethanol until further processing. Samples were embedded in
167 paraffin, cut at $3 \mu\text{m}$, and were stained with hematoxylin-eosin, or processed for detection of
168 cell proliferation by localizing proliferating cell nuclear antigen (**PCNA**) and cell apoptosis
169 using terminal deoxynucleotidyl transferase dUTP nick end labeling (**TUNEL**).

170

171 ***PCNA Localization.*** Deparaffinized rehydrated tissue slides were incubated in 3% H₂O₂ for
172 30 min to inhibit endogenous peroxidase. To unmask the antigens, tissue slides were placed in
173 a covered glass staining dish containing 10 mM citrate buffer (pH 6.0) and microwave heated
174 for 10 min. The slides were then incubated with bovine albumin in PBS (60 min) to block
175 nonspecific binding of antibodies. To stain PCNA, slides were then incubated with 100 μL of
176 diluted mouse monoclonal antibody to PCNA (clone PC10, BioGenex, San Ramon, CA)
177 overnight at 4 °C. In the morning, slides were incubated for 60 min at room temperature with
178 1:200 goat anti-mouse immunoglobulin biotin (DakoCytomation, Glostrup, Denmark) as a
179 secondary antibody. Slides were then incubated with 1:100 avidin-biotin preoxidase complex
180 (Immuno Pure ABC Peroxidase Staining kit Standard, Pierce Biotechnology, Rockford, IL)
181 for another 60 min at room temperature. Slides were incubated for 5 to 10 min with the
182 chromagen, 3,3'-diaminobenzidine tetrahydrochloride (Sigma, Madrid, Spain) in PBS
183 containing 0.04% hydrogen peroxide. Finally, slides were counterstained with hematoxylin.

184
185 ***Detection of Cell Death by TUNEL.*** A commercial kit (Apop Tag, Serologicals
186 Corporation, Norcross, GA) was used to visualize apoptotic cells. After deparaffinization and
187 rehydration, slides were incubated with proteinase K (20 μg/mL of PBS). Slides were
188 quenched with 2% H₂O₂ in PBS for 5 min, incubated in equilibration buffer for 20 min and
189 then incubated with terminal deoxynucleotidyl transferase for 60 min in a humidified chamber
190 at 37 °C. Slides were washed with stop / wash buffer for 20 min at room temperature and then
191 incubated with anti-digoxigenin-peroxidase for 30 min at room temperature in a humidified
192 chamber. Tissue sections were incubated for 5 to 10 min with 3,3'-diaminobenzidine
193 tetrahydrochloride (Sigma, Madrid, Spain) in PBS containing 0.04% hydrogen peroxide.
194 Sections were washed with distilled water and then counterstained with hematoxylin.

195

196 **Cell Counting.** Tissue sections were viewed by light microscopy (Olympus BH2, Olympus
197 Corporation, Tokyo, Japan) to quantify PCNA antigen expressing cells and apoptotic cells.
198 For each tissue section, 5 microscopic fields were quantified. A field was selected under low
199 power and slightly out of focus, then the objective was switched to greater power, a digital
200 image of the microscope field was taken at 100× magnification and cells were counted on a
201 computer monitor. On photographs of mammary tissue, number of cells per alveolus was
202 counted.

203

204 ***Statistical Analyses***

205 Data were analyzed by the PROC MIXED for repeated measurements of SAS (SAS 8.2;
206 SAS Inst. Inc., Cary, NC). The statistical mixed model contained the random effect of the
207 animal within the dry period length (treatment); the fixed effects of treatment and week of
208 lactation; the interaction between treatment and week of lactation; and the residual error. Milk
209 yield during 300 DIM of the previous lactation was used as a covariate. Data of milk
210 persistency, colostrum composition and mammary tissue parameters were analyzed by one
211 way ANOVA using PROC GLM with a model containing the effect of the treatment and the
212 residual error. Data were tested for the normality of distribution, and the logarithmic
213 transformation (\log_{10}) was used for IgG concentrations. Pearson's correlation coefficients
214 between colostrum components were also calculated.

215

216

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

217 According to the experimental treatments, D56 goats were dried off intentionally even
218 though they were still lactating. Of the 8 goats assigned to D0 treatment, only 3 goats (37%)
219 had a high continuous secretory activity and were able to maintain lactation until kidding for
220 unknown reasons. The other 5 goats decreased milk yield dramatically and stopped secretory

221 activity by themselves 4 wk before kidding (D27). Annen et al. (2004b) also described
222 spontaneous drying off in dairy cows submitted to continuous milking during advanced
223 pregnancy. Under the management conditions of our experiment, goats were milked once
224 daily and kept in pens during late lactation and advanced pregnancy (summer). With greater
225 daily milking frequency and mating at earlier lactation stage, more goats are expected to start
226 the subsequent lactation without spontaneous drying off. Actual length of the dry off period
227 were 56 ± 1 and 27 ± 4 d for D56 and D27, respectively. Kidding period for this study was 8 d
228 long.

229

230 ***Birth Weight of Kids and Colostrum Quality***

231 The D56 and D0 goats had similar kidding rate (2.40 kid/goat), but D27 kidded less than
232 D56 ($P < 0.05$; Table 1). Kids of D0 goats had lesser ($P < 0.05$) birth weight than kids of D56
233 and D27 (Table 1). This decrease in birth weight of D0 kids may be the consequence of the
234 nutritive stress resulting from the competition between lactation and pregnancy specially in
235 the last third of gestation when the fetal growth is greatest. Prepartum energy or protein
236 restriction reduced birth weight by 6 to 10% in goats (Sahlu et al., 1995). Alternatively, D0
237 goats that tolerated the omission of the dry period might have been able to resist the negative
238 effect of pregnancy because they were bearing fetuses with lighter weight. In dairy cows,
239 shortening or eliminating the dry period did not affect calf birth weight (Grummer and
240 Rastani, 2004). The impact of pregnancy on milk yield is partially thought to be because of
241 the secretion of estrogen by the fetal-placental unit (Bachman et al., 1988). Estradiol
242 concentration during pregnancy is proportional to the calf's birth weight (Guilbault et al.,
243 1985). Nevertheless, Gulay et al. (2003) suggested no effects of estrogen treatment on
244 mammary gland involution and milk yield in the subsequent lactation in dairy cows.

245 Specific gravity of D0 colostrum was **lesser** ($P < 0.01$) than in D56 and D27, indicating the
246 lower quality of colostrum from goats milked throughout pregnancy (Table 1). No values of
247 SG in the colostrum of goats are available to compare with our results. Colostral SG of D0
248 (1.032) was slightly **greater** than values for normal goat milk, which ranged from 1.022 to
249 1.026 (Guo et al., 2001). Measurement of colostral SG provides an inexpensive and practical
250 method for estimating colostral Ig concentration in cows (Fleenor and Stott, 1980). **Because**
251 kids of D0 had **lesser** birth weight and their mothers produced colostrum with low SG,
252 colostrum of D27 and D56 was used to feed those kids.

253 Colostrum of D0 goats contained a **lesser** ($P < 0.01$) concentration of IgG (5.6 mg/mL) than
254 D56 (42.4 mg/mL) and D27 (32.9 mg/mL) goats. Continuous milking adversely affected
255 colostrogenesis and resulted in colostrum with a low concentration of IgG in D0 goats in our
256 experiment. Approaching parturition, massive selective transfer of blood IgG into the
257 colostrum in dry mammary gland causes a high concentration of IgG in the colostrum
258 (Brandon and Lascelles, 1975). This selective transfer of IgG is locally controlled by
259 mammary epithelial cells and when milk secretion is maintained, this selective transfer
260 decreased (Guy et al., 1994). Therefore, continuous milking during pregnancy in D0 goats in
261 our study maintained the activity of mammary epithelial cells, preventing the accumulation of
262 IgG in D0 colostrum.

263 The IgG concentration in colostrum of D0 (5.6 mg/mL) was greater than the concentration
264 reported by Levieux et al. (2002) in the normal goat milk (0.20 to 2.21 mg/mL). Nevertheless,
265 this concentration seems to be insufficient to achieve the recommended serum **concentration**
266 of IgG in newborn kids (> 12 mg/mL; O'Brien and Sherman, 1993). In addition, a positive
267 correlation ($r = 0.86$) was found between the concentration of IgG in the colostrum and in the
268 serum of newborn kids (Argüello et al., 2004). In the case of omitting the dry period, a very
269 large amount of colostrum has to be fed to supply kids with sufficient mass of IgG. Large

270 amounts of colostrum containing a low concentration of IgG, however, would not be absorbed
271 adequately (Stott and Fellah, 1983).

272 The IgG concentrations did not vary between D27 and D56 goats (Table 1), and ranged
273 from 23.5 to 64.0 mg/mL (overall mean, 39.6 mg/mL). In accordance with our results, the
274 immunologic quality of colostrum was similar between dairy cows dried off for 30 or 70d
275 (Gulay et al., 2005).

276 Casein constituted 28.2, 28.1 and 63.1% of total protein in the colostrum of D56, D27 and
277 D0, respectively. Colostrum of D0 was close to normal goat milk in the Murciano-Granadina
278 breed, where CN represents 75% of total milk protein (Salama et al., 2003). Whey protein,
279 most of which is Ig, constitutes over two-thirds of total protein in the colostrum of D56 and
280 D27 and was greater ($P < 0.01$) than in D0 (Table 1).

281 As far as we know, correlations among IgG concentration, SG and other components of the
282 colostrum have not been reported before in dairy goats (Table 2). Excluding values of D0,
283 concentrations of IgG correlated positively with SG ($r = 0.88$; $P < 0.001$), which was similar
284 to the 0.84 reported by Fleenor and Stott (1980) in dairy cows, but greater than the 0.53
285 reported by Morin et al. (2001) in cows. Colostral SG was more correlated ($P < 0.001$) with
286 concentrations of protein ($r = 0.96$) and whey protein ($r = 0.95$) than with IgG concentration.
287 The same observation was reported by Morin et al. (2001) who showed the limitations of
288 using colostral SG as an indicator of IgG concentration in bovine colostrum.

289

290 ***Milk Yield***

291 Data of milk yield for lactation that preceded the dry period and lactation that followed the
292 dry period are shown in Figure 1 and Table 3.

293

294 ***Preceding Lactation.*** Goats that tolerated continuous milking throughout pregnancy were
295 not the best milk producers during the first 29 wk of the preceding lactation (2.25, 2.12, and
296 1.98 L/d for D56, D27 and D0, respectively). The D0 goats, **however**, produced more ($P <$
297 0.01) milk than D27 during wk 43 and 44 of lactation. Milk persistency was similar among
298 groups before pregnancy, but decreased as pregnancy advanced with D0 goats having the
299 **greatest** milk persistency during the third and fourth mo of pregnancy (Table 3).

300 In the last 3 wk before parturition, milk yield increased for D0 goats (Figure 1). Circulating
301 prolactin in dairy goats remained low up to d 120 of pregnancy and increased during the last
302 part of pregnancy (Kornalijnslijper et al., 1997). Similarly, an increase in milk yield during
303 the days preceding calving was observed in dairy cows (Wheelock et al., 1965), although
304 Remond et al. (1992) did not detect such an increase.

305

306 ***Subsequent Lactation.*** Due to omitting the dry period, D0 goats produced 16% less ($P <$
307 0.01) milk in the subsequent lactation than they did in the previous lactation. Moreover, milk
308 yield of D0 goats in the subsequent lactation was reduced ($P < 0.05$) by 21 and 29%
309 compared with the yield of D56 and D27 goats, respectively (Figure 1 and Table 3). On the
310 other hand, D27 and D56 goats in the subsequent lactation produced 15% ($P < 0.01$) and 4%
311 ($P = 0.122$), respectively more milk than they did in the equivalent period in the previous
312 lactation. Omitting the dry period in dairy cows also reduced milk production in the
313 subsequent lactation by 15 to 40% (Swanson, 1965; Remond et al., 1992; Rastani et al.,
314 2005), although bST administration alleviated these losses in multiparous cows (Annen et
315 al., 2004a).

316 Fowler et al. (1991) with the half-udder design, reported that the dry period between
317 lactation is not necessary in Saanen dairy goats. In the latter study, half udders were dried off
318 2 wk before mating (dry period lasted 23 wk), which is unusual and 3 times the length of the

319 dry period in our study. Additionally, when 1 half udder was dried off, activity and number of
320 mammary cells increased in the lactating half within the same udder (Capuco and Akers,
321 1990), and involution is partially inhibited in the non-lactating half (Akers and Keys, 1985).
322 In our study both udder halves were dried off for a shorter period when goats were in late
323 lactation and advanced pregnancy, which might explain the discrepancy with the results of
324 Fowler et al. (1991).

325 Milk persistency was numerically **greater** ($P = 0.25$) in D0 than in D56 and D27 (Table 3).
326 Comparing D56 and D0, milk yield was 24% **lesser** in D0 ($P < 0.05$) in the first 20 wk of
327 lactation and 14% **lesser** ($P = 0.097$) in wk 21 to 30 of lactation (Figure 1 and Table 3).
328 Similarly, milk of cows with no dry period (Remond et al., 1997) or with a 30-d dry period
329 (Bachman, 2002) persisted more than in cows with the conventional 60-d dry period.

330 No differences in milk yield were detected between D56 and D27 groups indicating that the
331 shorter dry periods (i.e. 27 d) are sufficient for mammary involution in goats. **Consequently,**
332 **no negative effects are expected when goats spontaneously dried off or are dried intentionally**
333 **1 mo before kidding.** Capuco et al. (1997) showed that mammary growth in cows was
334 initiated within the first 25 d of the 60-d dry period. Moreover, cows with a 30-d dry period
335 produced similar milk yield as cows with the 60-d dry period (Bachman, 2002).

336

337 ***Mammary Cell Turnover***

338 Indices of apoptosis and proliferation in D56 goats at 284 DIM of the preceding lactation, 7
339 d after drying off, and 48 DIM of the subsequent lactation are shown in Figure 2. Cellular
340 indices of apoptosis (0.61%) and proliferation (2.52%) did not vary between mammary
341 biopsies of d 284 and d 48 of the preceding and subsequent lactations, respectively. Our
342 values of apoptosis are in the range (0.2 to 3.0%) reported in lactating cows (Capuco et al.,
343 2001; Colitti et al., 2004; Norgaard et al., 2005) and lactating goats (Li et al., 1999). Similar

344 to our values of proliferation, cells expressing PCNA accounted for 0.17 to 2.99% of
345 mammary cells during lactation in dairy cows (Colitti et al., 2004; Norgaard et al., 2005). In
346 our results, cell proliferation exceeds cell death, which gives the impression that the
347 mammary gland grows throughout lactation rather than regresses. The TUNEL test detects the
348 proportion of cells dying at a given moment before being phagocytosized by macrophages
349 and adjacent alveolar cells, whereas PCNA indicates proliferating cells for approximately 24
350 h (Knight, 2000). In addition, milk may be a vehicle for the elimination of mammary
351 apoptotic cells in addition to phagocytosis. We observed some apoptotic cells in the alveolar
352 lumen and most of these cells were localized in the alveolar epithelium (Figure 3) as
353 previously reported in ewes (Tatarczuch et al., 1997).

354 Comparing d 284 (late lactation) with d 7 after dry off (involution) in D56 goats, an
355 increase in mammary apoptosis (0.51 to 1.75%; $P < 0.06$) and proliferation (2.09 to 7.12%; P
356 < 0.05) was observed (Figure 2). Similarly, Li et al. (1999) observed that the apoptosis index
357 was less than 1% of cells in lactating tissues and increased at wk 1 (2 to 3%) and 2 (5%) after
358 drying off in nonpregnant goats.

359 The peak of apoptosis probably occurred before d 7 of involution in our goats because they
360 were in late pregnancy at drying off. Annen et al. (2003) detected the **greatest** incidence of
361 apoptosis in pregnant cows at d 2 after drying off, and by d 8 the number of apoptotic cells
362 did not differ from lactating values. High apoptosis and proliferation indices during dry off in
363 our results indicate significant mammary cell turnover as previously observed by Capuco et
364 al. (1997) in dairy cows, where the proliferation of mammary epithelial cells in dry cows was
365 **greater** than in cows without dry off to replace senescent and damaged cells.

366 In the subsequent lactation (48 DIM), number of cells per alveolus in D56 ($P = 0.14$) and
367 D27 ($P = 0.19$) goats was greater than in D0 goats (Table 4) in accordance with milk yield
368 **values**. In our results, milk yield correlated positively with cell number per alveolus ($r = 0.81$;

369 $P < 0.05$). No differences were detected between groups in apoptosis or proliferation indices
370 for D56, D27 and D0, respectively (Table 4). Our results indicate that the length of the dry off
371 period did not affect mammary cell turnover in the following lactation.

372 The absence of the dry period, **however**, might have negatively affected cell renewal before
373 kidding in D0 goats, **because** these goats tended to have a **lesser** ($P < 0.20$) number of cells
374 per alveolus than D56 and D27 goats in the subsequent lactation (Table 4). Fitzgerald et al.
375 (2004) observed that proliferation of mammary epithelial cells in glands of primiparous dairy
376 cows dried off for 60 d was greater than in glands without dry off at 7 d before calving. These
377 authors reported no differences in cell proliferation between glands with or without dry off
378 after parturition, **suggesting** that reduced cell proliferation before parturition caused milk yield
379 losses in the subsequent lactation in glands without dry off.

380

381

CONCLUSIONS

382 Omitting dry period between lactations in Murciano-Granadina dairy goats had negative
383 effects on milk production, probably **because of** impaired cellular replacement during dry off,
384 and is not recommended in practice. Milking during late pregnancy reduced kid birth weight
385 and the immunologic quality of the colostrum, which could negatively affect kid survival.
386 Goats dried off spontaneously for 27 d before kidding were as productive as those goats dried
387 off for 56 d and the colostrum quality was similar.

388

389

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498 whole pregnancy on the composition of cow's milk. *J. Dairy Res.* 32:249-254.
- 499

500 **Table 1.** Effect of dry period length on the birth weight of kids, colostrum specific gravity
 501 and colostrum composition in dairy goats

Item	Dry period length ¹		
	D56 (n = 9)	D27 (n = 5)	D0 (n = 3)
Kidding rate, kids/goat	2.46 ^a ± 0.18	1.80 ^b ± 0.23	2.33 ^{ab} ± 0.29
Kids birth weight, kg	2.14 ^a ± 0.10	2.25 ^a ± 0.14	1.73 ^b ± 0.16
Colostrum			
Specific gravity	1.053 ^a ± 0.002	1.048 ^a ± 0.003	1.032 ^b ± 0.004
Log IgG, mg/mL	1.61 ^a ± 0.04	1.51 ^a ± 0.06	0.74 ^b ± 0.07
Total solids, %	23.0 ^a ± 1.0	20.1 ^{ab} ± 1.5	15.7 ^b ± 1.9
Fat, %	6.37 ± 0.39	5.78 ± 0.61	6.28 ± 0.78
Protein, %	13.19 ^a ± 0.75	10.52 ^a ± 1.15	4.34 ^b ± 1.49
Casein, %	3.64 ± 0.20	2.92 ± 0.31	2.77 ± 0.39
Casein, % of protein	28.2 ^b ± 1.9	28.1 ^b ± 2.9	63.1 ^a ± 3.8
Whey protein, %	9.05 ^a ± 0.66	7.18 ^a ± 1.02	1.28 ^b ± 1.31
NPN, %	0.51 ^a ± 0.02	0.42 ^b ± 0.04	0.29 ^c ± 0.04

502 ¹ Dried off for 56 d (D56), dried off spontaneously for 27 d (D27), or without dry off (D0).

503 ^{a,b,c} Means with different superscripts within row differ ($P < 0.05$).

504 **Table 2.** Correlation coefficients of colostral IgG, protein fractions, fat, total solids and
 505 specific gravity in dairy goats dried off for 56 or 27 d before kidding (n = 14)

	Total solids	Fat	Total protein	True protein	Casein	Whey protein	NPN	Specific gravity
IgG	0.85 ^{***}	0.44	0.91 ^{***}	0.91 ^{***}	0.51 [*]	0.92 ^{***}	0.38	0.88 ^{***}
Total solids		0.76 ^{***}	0.93 ^{***}	0.93 ^{***}	0.74 ^{***}	0.86 ^{***}	0.45	0.85 ^{***}
Fat			0.48	0.47	0.62 ^{**}	0.37	0.39	0.32
Total protein				0.99 ^{***}	0.64 ^{**}	0.97 ^{***}	0.43	0.96 ^{***}
True protein					0.63 ^{**}	0.97 ^{***}	0.40	0.95 ^{***}
Casein						0.45	0.55 [*]	0.57 [*]
Whey protein							0.30	0.95 ^{***}
NPN								0.31

506 ^{*} $P < 0.05$
 507 ^{**} $P < 0.01$
 508 ^{***} $P < 0.001$
 509

510 **Table 3.** Effect of dry period length on milk yield and milk persistency in dairy goats

Item	Dry period length ¹		
	D56 (n = 9)	D27 (n = 5)	D0 (n = 3)
Parity number	2.75 ± 0.41	3.00 ± 0.63	2.67 ± 0.67
Preceding lactation			
Milk yield, L/d			
wk 2 to wk 29	2.25 ± 0.10	2.12 ± 0.13	1.98 ± 0.16
wk 30 to wk 42	1.50 ± 0.11	1.46 ± 0.13	1.65 ± 0.16
wk 43 to wk 46	...	0.15 ^b ± 0.10	0.96 ^a ± 0.14
wk 47 to wk 50	0.75 ± 0.10
Milk persistency, %			
Before pregnancy ²	67.6 ± 2.3	64.2 ± 2.9	69.7 ± 3.8
mo 3 of pregnancy ³	26.0 ^b ± 2.7	27.6 ^b ± 3.5	45.3 ^a ± 4.5
mo 4 of pregnancy ⁴	...	4.8 ^b ± 3.6	34.0 ^a ± 6.6
Subsequent lactation			
Milk yield, L/d			
wk 2 to wk 20	2.35 ^a ± 0.12	2.60 ^a ± 0.16	1.79 ^b ± 0.20
wk 21 to wk 30	2.05 ^{ab} ± 0.08	2.32 ^a ± 0.10	1.76 ^b ± 0.12
wk 2 to wk 30	2.24 ^a ± 0.10	2.51 ^a ± 0.13	1.78 ^b ± 0.16
Milk persistency ⁵ , %	65.1 ± 4.6	66.5 ± 5.8	75.8 ± 7.5

511 ¹ Dried off for 56 d (D56), dried off spontaneously for 27 d (D27), or without dry off (D0).

512 ² Milk yield during wk 26 to 29 / milk yield during wk 2 to 6.

513 ³ Milk yield during wk 39 to 42 / milk yield during wk 2 to 6.

514 ⁴ Milk yield during wk 43 to 46 / milk yield during wk 2 to 6.

515 ⁵ Milk yield during wk 27 to 30 / milk yield during wk 2 to 6.

516 ^{a,b} Means with different superscripts within row differ ($P < 0.05$).

517 **Table 4.** Effect of preceding dry period length on the number of epithelial cells per alveolus
 518 and indices of apoptosis and proliferation in the mammary gland of dairy goats at 48 DIM

Item	Dry period length ¹		
	D56 (n = 3)	D27 (n = 3)	D0 (n = 3)
Milk yield, L/d	2.43 ^a ± 0.23	2.74 ^a ± 0.19	1.85 ^b ± 0.25
Cell number per alveolus	38.6 ± 7.1	36.3 ± 7.0	24.1 ± 5.0
Apoptotic cells, %	0.71 ± 0.28	0.68 ± 0.28	0.65 ± 0.23
Proliferating cells, %	2.95 ± 1.04	1.37 ± 1.04	2.48 ± 0.85

519 ¹ Dried off for 56 d (D56), dried off spontaneously for 27 d (D27), or without dry off (D0).

520 ^{a,b} Means with different superscripts within row differ ($P < 0.05$).

521

522 **Figure 1.** Milk yield of all dairy goats during the pre-experimental period (\square ; $n = 17$). At wk
523 42 of lactation, goats were divided into 2 groups: goats that were dried off for 56 d (\circ ; $n = 9$)
524 and goats without dry off ($n = 8$). At wk 47 of lactation, 5 of the 8 goats assigned to no dry off
525 dried off spontaneously for 27 d (Δ ; $n = 5$), and the rest were continuously milked (\blacktriangle ; $n = 3$).

526

527

528 **Figure 2.** Apoptosis (○) and proliferation (■) indices in dairy goats lactated for 300 d and
529 dried off for 56 d before kidding (n = 3). Biopsies were taken at late lactation (284 DIM),
530 during involution (7 d after drying off) and early lactation (48 DIM in the subsequent
531 lactation).

532

533

534 **Figure 3.** Identification of apoptotic cells in the mammary gland of dairy goats at wk 7 of
535 lactation. Apoptotic cells (arrows) were mainly localized in the alveolar epithelial cells (A)
536 and some were in the alveolar lumen (B).

